

A Network-based Intrusion Detection System based on widely used Cybersecurity Datasets and State of the Art ML techniques

Efthymios Chondrogiannis¹, Efstathios Karanastasis¹, Vassiliki Andronikou¹ and Theodora Varvarigou¹

¹ Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, Athens, Greece
{chondrog, ekaranas, vandro, doravarv}@mail.ntua.gr

Abstract. Modern software systems consist of several entities that interact among each other through the Web, and hence are vulnerable to potential malicious activities. Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) intend to monitor such systems and/or their sub-systems, including the network infrastructure, and identify malicious user behaviour on time, so that the appropriate measures can be taken to protect the relevant entities or mitigate the consequences. However, user behaviour is often quite complicated and cannot be captured by simple rules. Machine Learning (ML) techniques provide the means for automatically detecting potential intrusions based on previously collected data. In this article, a Network-based IDS is presented, which can detect several network attacks through the usage of ML techniques and relevant frameworks. The publicly available cybersecurity datasets that were used in this work are introduced and their contribution for intrusion detection purposes is evaluated. Also, the approach followed for dealing with false alarms and new attack types is presented and the relevant findings are discussed.

Keywords: Network-based Intrusion Detection, Cybersecurity Datasets, Machine Learning, Network Security, Artificial Intelligence.

1 Introduction

Modern software systems consist of several entities that are often accessible or communicate with each other through the Web, and hence are vulnerable to potential intrusion attempts. Firewalls protect networks and systems from malicious activities by continuously monitoring network traffic and allowing/blocking incoming or outgoing network packets using predetermined security rules. Nevertheless, advanced threats can bypass firewalls and cause serious damages to the normal functioning of the respective entities. Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) serve as another line of defence with their role being the on-time detection of potential malicious activities so that the network/systems administrators can take the appropriate actions for the protection of the systems and data from unauthorised access, alteration or destruction, or the miti-

gation of the consequences. Hence, IDSs are of paramount importance for protecting the valuable digital assets of any organisation.

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) can be organised in two broad categories, i.e., network-based and host-based, based on the type of data being used for identifying potential intrusion attempts [1]. In the first case, the IDS monitors the network packets being exchanged whereas in the second case the IDS focuses on the data being produced by the OS of hosts and/or relevant applications. The IDS techniques used for detecting potential attacks may rely on the signatures of existing/known attacks (signature-based or misuse-based techniques) or deviations of the data collected from the ones that correspond to normal system behaviour (anomaly-based techniques). In many cases, a hybrid approach is followed that can overcome the shortcomings of the two aforementioned techniques.

Existing network-based IDS (NIDS) such as Snort¹ can detect potential threats based on the rules specified. However, in many cases, malicious user behaviour is quite complex and hence it cannot be properly handled by one or more user-defined rules. Machine Learning (ML) and Data Mining (DM) techniques (described in section 2.1) have a distinct role in the intrusion detection process, since they enable software agents to automatically extract knowledge from data (e.g., frequent patterns, clusters and/or ML models) that can be accordingly used for intrusion detection purposes. This process can be facilitated through the utilisation of existing publicly available cybersecurity datasets (described in section 2.2) that contain several parameters extracted from network flows along with a label that indicates if they come from normal or abnormal behaviour. However, their usefulness should be evaluated, since these data may often be obsolete and/or come from a simulation process and hence pose significant differences to the ones extracted from real network traffic.

In this work, we present the approach followed and the network-based intrusion detection system developed using ML techniques and publicly available cybersecurity datasets. In the core of the intrusion detection process is the ML model developed using annotated datasets that may come from either existing cybersecurity datasets or (additionally) network data collected from real network traffic. The evaluation of the developed NIDS using both data coming from cybersecurity datasets and new ones, indicated that it can adequately serve its purposes, while it can easily handle potential changes to user behaviour and new types of network attacks through a semi-automatic update process.

The document is organised as follows. In section 2, state-of-the-art ML and DM techniques along with widely-used cybersecurity datasets are presented. In section 3, the approach followed and the Network-based ML-driven IDS developed is analytically described. In section 4, the evaluation of the ML models developed through the usage of both existing cybersecurity datasets and real network traffic is presented and relevant issues are discussed. Finally, in section 5, the main contribution of this work is summarised.

¹ Snort - Network Intrusion Detection & Prevention System, available at <https://www.snort.org/>

2 Related Work

2.1 ML and DM techniques for Intrusion Detection

Machine Learning (ML) and Data Mining (DM) techniques [2] are a vital component of cybersecurity systems, especially for detecting incoming, previously unknown attacks. These techniques are often used in the context of a Knowledge Discovery System that applies different algorithms that belong to the ML or DM field for extracting data patterns that could potentially signify a security attack.

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Decision Trees (DTs) are widely used for intrusion detection purposes [3]. SVMs intend to find a hyperplane that separates the data in two categories so that their distance from this hyperplane is maximised (in contrast with Logistic Regression – a particular type of Generalised Linear Model – that searches for a hyperplane that separates them). Therefore, SVMs are suitable for binary classification problems and, depending on the choice of an associated kernel, they can perform quite well even when the data are not linearly separable. DTs focus on the discrimination power of the dataset features to build a tree-like structure that is accordingly used for classification purposes.

Other notable ML techniques are Bayesian Networks (BNs) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). BNs are probabilistic graphical networks that represent the variables and the relations among them as a graph, with the simplest one being the Naive Bayes (NB) classifier. The latter assumes that the parameters/features are independent of each other and only depend on the class of data. ANNs consist of several interconnected artificial neurons that utilise the information gained from the nodes of the previous layer for the classification of input data. Especially Deep Neural Networks can automatically extract features from raw data (e.g., network packets) and accordingly use them for classification purposes. Their usage has been significantly increased since 2015 [4]. The K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) algorithm has been also used for intrusion detection purposes [5]. This lazy learning algorithm detects the K entities that are nearest the given data and accordingly uses them for predicting the appropriate label (in case of a classification problem).

The aforementioned ML models can be combined for making better predictions (aka ensemble learning). For instance, the Random Forest (RF) - a characteristic example of a bagging method - consists of several DTs that are developed in parallel, based on a subset of the given data (randomly sampled with replacement) and a subset of available features as well, with notable results. The AdaBoost (AB) algorithm - a boosting method - is based on several “weak” classifiers that are trained one after the outcome of the previous one so that they can accordingly focus on those samples that are not correctly satisfied. Stacking methods intend to develop a meta-model that combines the outcome of several independently-designed classifiers for producing the final outcome.

The performance of ML models depends on several parameters (aka hyper-parameters) that are often manually specified after making several tests. Automatically detecting their appropriate values, so that the ML model performance is maximised, is not a trivial task, especially when several combinations of them should be

examined. Bayesian Optimisation [6] facilitates solving the Hyperparameters Optimisation Problem and in combination with Meta-Learning techniques and Automatic Ensemble Construction can minimise the role of the ML expert in the ML model development process (AutoML). In fact, the selection of the appropriate algorithm and the detection of the appropriate parameters can be described as one problem known as Combined Algorithm Selection and Hyperparameters Optimisation (CASH) problem [7].

Clustering methods [8] intend to find patterns in highly dimensional data with the most widely known methods being hierarchical clustering (i.e., a particular case of connectivity models) and K-means clustering (i.e., a particular case of centroid models). Density models such as the DBSCAN [9] group the data points in such way that their outcome consists of dense and connected regions. Frequently Pattern (FP) and Association Rules Mining techniques are used to discover previously unknown patterns and association rules from the data. The Apriori algorithm [10] detects all sets of items that appear more frequently than a predefined threshold (support) and accordingly generates association rules based on these item sets, conditioned on the constraint that the element(s) on the left side of the rule appear more frequently than another predefined threshold (confidence). The FP-Growth algorithm [11] creates a compact representation of the transaction data recorded in a relational database in the form of a tree that facilitates the detection of the FPs.

2.2 Cybersecurity Datasets

There are several intrusion detection datasets with the most widely used being the NSL-KDD dataset [12][13]. This dataset is an improved version of the KDD Cup 1999 dataset² and is very useful for testing ML techniques, since it contains almost 149 thousand records with 41 features extracted from the analysis of both network traffic and background host processes coming from either normal user behaviour or one out of four different type of network attacks, i.e., Denial of Service (DoS), Probe, Root to Local (R2L) and User to Root (U2R). On the other hand, the development of this dataset was based on the data retrieved before more than two decades ago. Additionally, only a very limited number of the dataset features are relevant with the ones that can be potentially extracted from real network traffic and background system processes, and hence this dataset is not very useful in practice.

A more contemporary cybersecurity dataset that has been also mentioned by several authors is the CICIDS-2017 [14]. This dataset was developed based on the network traffic collected from a particular infrastructure developed during five consecutive days of July 2017. For this purpose, several publicly available software tools were used for generating realistic background traffic and executing a diverse set of attack scenarios. The data collected were aggregated to network flows and several network traffic features were extracted/calculated using the CICFlowMeter³ tool. The outcome of this process was recorded to CSV files that contain more than 2.8 million records

² KDD Cup 1999 Data, available at <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html>

³ CICFlowMeter, available at <https://github.com/ahlashkari/CICFlowMeter>

in total with almost 80 features for each one of them, including a Label with the particular network attack.

Another dataset for intrusion detection purposes is the UNSW-NB15 [15]. This dataset was developed based on both normal and abnormal the network traffic generated using the IXIA's PerfectStorm⁴ tool on January 22 and February 17, 2015. Network packets exchanged were recorded to PCAP files and were further processed using publicly available tools and custom C# programs for detecting the network flows and extracting several features for each one of them, which were organised in five categories, i.e., flow features, basic features, content features, time features and additional features. The outcome of this process was recorded to CSV files that contain almost 2.5 million network flows in total, with 49 features for each one of them.

Many other cybersecurity datasets are available on the Web, such as ISCX-2012 and LITNET-2020 to name a few. For more information about them, we prompt readers to papers [16] and [17]. Apart from the aforementioned datasets, there are several publicly available PCAP files⁵ about known security attacks, which could be also useful for IDS evaluation purposes.

3 Methodology

3.1 Approach and System Overview

The NIDS developed monitors network traffic with its primal goal being the detection of suspicious activities, so that the network administrators can be informed in order to perform further investigations and take the appropriate actions. For this purpose, the NFStream Python Framework was used, as shown in Fig. 1. This framework aggregates network packets into network flows based on a few parameters, such as the source and destination IP addresses and port numbers, and accordingly extracts several network traffic features, such as the total number of bytes of the respective network packets and the network flow duration [18].

Fig. 1. Network-based Intrusion Detection System Using ML techniques.

⁴ IXIA's PerfectStorm tool, <http://www.ixiacom.com/products/perfectstorm>

⁵ Publicly available PCAP files, <https://www.netresec.com/?page=PcapFiles>

The NFStream was properly configured so that 79 parameters are extracted for each new network flow⁶. Nevertheless, a subset of them is actually used for intrusion detection purposes, taking into account the ones used by the ML model. For this purpose, a mapping process takes place so that a new record is created with the specific parameters being necessary for intrusion detection purposes in the appropriate order. Accordingly, a pre-trained ML model is used (analytically described in the subsection 3.2) that can distinguish normal (0) from abnormal (1) network traffic. The output of this ML model along with the date-time and the values of the aforementioned parameters (i.e., including the ones being used and the rest ones) are recorded in a CSV file (in append-only mode) so that they can be accordingly presented by a GUI (available to authorised users). The data recorded can be also used by the network administrator for improving the performance of the system, especially when a considerable number of Type I/II errors are observed (presented in the subsection 3.3).

3.2 ML Model Development & Evaluation Process

In the core of the intrusion detection process is the ML model that examines the particular features of network flows in order to identify potential abnormal user behaviour and accordingly inform the network administrator. The design of this ML model was driven by the data published in CICIDS-17⁷. More precisely, we downloaded the CSV files, read their content and merged them in one data frame. Accordingly, we removed the records with missing or infinity values as well as those with inappropriate values (i.e., negative or extremely large values). The outcome of the aforementioned process was a data frame that contains 2.825 million records. Many of them (i.e., 80.31 %) come from normal user behaviour, whereas only 1/5 of the records (i.e., 19.69 %) come from an attack.

The above dataset was balanced before being used for the development of ML models. Since there is a considerable amount of abnormal records already available, we randomly selected the same number of records from normal network flows and merged them, creating a dataset that contains 1.113 million records with 77 features for each one of them. Additionally, we computed the Information Gain for each feature and accordingly selected the ones (i.e., 55 features) with a value above a threshold (i.e., 0.05), as presented in Fig. 2. In this figure we also annotated the CICIDS-17 features aligned with the ones available by NFStream framework and the features available at the USNW-NB15 dataset. Also, their values were normalised so that they belong in the range [0, 1]. Afterwards, this dataset was split in three distinct datasets, i.e., for training (containing 70% of the data), validation (10% of data) and testing (20% of data) purposes.

⁶ NFStream - APIs Documentation, available at <https://www.nfstream.org/docs/api>

⁷ CICIDS2017 dataset, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/cicdataset/cicids2017>

Fig. 2. The most important features of the CICIDS 17 dataset (based on 10% of records) along with the ones mapped with NFlowstream framework and UNSW-NB15 dataset.

Then, the datasets were used for the development of three different ML models that serve different purposes (Fig. 3). In the first ML model, all the aforementioned features were used. In the second ML model (i.e., the one integrated with the NIDS), we used only 30 CICIDS-17 features which were aligned with the parameters that can be automatically extracted from network traffic using NFlowstream [19]. In the third ML model, we used only 8 CICIDS-17 features that were aligned with the features available at the UNSW-NB15 dataset⁸. For each one of the aforementioned three cases, several ML models were developed (i.e., NB, SVM, DT, ANN, kNN, RF, AB) and accordingly the most appropriate one was selected, based on the particular evaluation metrics computed. For the development of each ML model, we used the training dataset for automatically specifying the internal parameters of the respective ML model, whereas the validation dataset was used for measuring its performance based on the hyper-parameters values and hence for selecting the most appropriate ones.

Fig. 3. ML Models Development and Evaluation Process.

⁸ UNSW-NB 15 dataset, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/mrwellsdavid/unswnb15>

For the evaluation of the developed ML models, we used accuracy (since the dataset was balanced) as well as precision, recall and F-measure (aka F1-score). In the first case (i.e., when all available features were used), the evaluation of the developed ML model was based solely on the testing dataset (i.e., randomly selected data from the same dataset). In the second and third case, the model was evaluated using both the aforementioned testing dataset and other data extracted from publicly available PCAP files⁹ with network attacks and the UNSW-NB15 dataset respectively. In both cases, a similar process was followed for the extraction of data residing in the corresponding Files and the development of a dataset for ML model evaluation purposes. Since the data extracted from the two aforementioned sources were unbalanced and quite limited (especially in case of datasets developed from PCAP files with network attacks), the SMOTE [20] method was used for the development of a balanced dataset. Also, additional models were developed based on the data residing only to the respective datasets so that we could evaluate whether and/or to which extent the knowledge transfer is feasible. The results are presented in Section 4.

3.3 ML Model Revision

The network administrators can further examine the selected ML model (using, for instance, data coming from honeypots) and update it if being necessary, such as in case of false alarms or missed attacks. This can be done through a semi-automatic process that includes the enrichment of the initial training dataset being used (i.e., CICIDS-17 dataset) with new records coming from real network traffic (as already described in the subsection 3.1), and the development and selection of the appropriate ML model. For this purpose, randomly selected records from the initial dataset should be replaced with the new ones, so that the size of the dataset remains the same. In advance, the data recorded from the real network traffic should be annotated with the appropriate label (i.e., 0 for normal traffic or 1 for abnormal traffic) taking into account whether an attack occurred or not, during a specific period of time. Accordingly, a new ML model can be developed, following the same process with the one described in the previous sub-section. The new model along with the particular features used can be stored in a file, so that it can be accordingly used by the NIDS.

The above process can be applied in two different cases. In the first case, we assume that the network administrators have noticed several false alarms and hence they would like to update the ML model used by the NIDS. For this purpose, the initial dataset should be enriched with the data coming from normal network traffic, before being used for training the ML model. In the second case, we assume that a new attack had taken place during a particular period of time that was not detected by the NIDS, and hence the network administrators would like to update the ML model. In this case, the relevant data from the network attack should be included in the dataset before they are used for training purposes. An example is presented in Section 4.2 and especially the impact that the new data have in the overall accuracy of the ML model.

⁹ Publicly available PCAP files, <https://sugarent.tistory.com/m/459>

4 Results & Discussion

4.1 ML Models Evaluation

Fig. 4 presents the accuracy of several ML models developed based on the data available at the CICIDS-17 CSV files using 7 different ML techniques (i.e., Gaussian NB - GNB, DT, SVM, ANN, KNN, RF, AB) and 3 different subsets of CICIDS-17 features. In particular, in the first case, we used all the important CICIDS-17 features (i.e., 55 based on the mutual information) whereas in the other two cases we focused on a subset of these features that can be aligned with the ones extracted using NFStream framework and the ones available by the USNW-NB15 datasets respectively. As can be noticed, several ML models can achieve outstanding outcomes when being evaluated using the data stored in the testing dataset (i.e., a separate dataset from the one being used for training purposes) with the best performance (in terms of both accuracy and total execution time) observed by the Random Forest (RF) classifier. The results are in accordance with the ones presented in the work [21]. Nevertheless, in our work much more ML techniques were taken into consideration.

Fig. 4. Accuracy of ML models developed using 7 different ML techniques based on the CICIDS-17 Testing Dataset when being trained using different subsets of CICIDS-17 features.

Fig. 5 presents the confusion matrix along with several other evaluation metrics of the RF classifier based on the aforementioned subsets of CICIDS-17 features. Obviously, when all the important features are used the accuracy is maximized. Nevertheless, even when a limited number of features are being used, the accuracy remains high and the RF classifier can accurately distinguish both normal and abnormal network flows. This occurs since the features are highly related with each other, as presented in Fig. 6. Hence, despite the fact that the most important features (i.e., average packet size) has not been mapped with NFStream, the accuracy of the RF is high, since the next feature (i.e., Packet Length Std.) is mapped and is highly correlated with the aforementioned one.

Fig. 5. Confusion Matrix and other Evaluation Metrics of the RF classifier based on the CICIDS-17 Testing Dataset when being trained using different subsets of CICIDS-17 features.

Fig. 6. Pearson's correlation Matrix of important CICIDS-17 features.

4.2 ML Models Further Evaluation and Update

Fig. 7 presents the evaluation of two of the aforementioned RF classifiers (i.e., the ones developed for NFStream framework and USNW-NB15 dataset) when being used to distinguish normal from abnormal behaviour captured in files coming from a different source (i.e., the protected system) than the one used for their training. As can be noticed, most of the records available at the USNW-NB15 dataset and the one developed using the NFStream framework and PCAP files with known attacks are considered to be normal. Hence, a lot of network attacks can go unnoticed. However, we observed that when using data from the same source for training purposes, the RF classifier can perform very well, which indicates that the selected features are enough for distinguishing potential intrusion attempts.

Fig. 7. Confusion Matrixes and other Evaluation Metrics (a) Evaluation of the RF classifier developed using data coming from different dataset; (b) Evaluation of the RF classifier developed based on data coming from the same dataset.

The performance of the CICIDS-17 RF classifier is significantly increased when a limited number of records from the new data source are included in the initial CICIDS-17 dataset. As presented in Fig. 8, the performance of the RF classifier in-

creases to 99% when 1% of records from the dataset developed using PCAP files from the actual protected data source are added in the initial CICIDS-17 balanced dataset.

Fig. 8. (a) Accuracy of the RF classifier when the training dataset is enriched with additional records from known Network Attacks; (b) Confusion Matrix and Other Evaluation Metrics of the RF classifier when 5% of new records were added to the CICIDS-17 dataset.

The above analysis indicated that the performance of the developed ML models can be significantly increased if evidence arises that they are not performing as expected when used in practice for detecting real network attacks in a particular system. This can be achieved via a process that includes the maintenance and updating of the initial dataset with new records from the actual protected system, and re-training of the ML model used. The semi-automatic nature of this process can significantly facilitate the network administrator's tasks and its outcome can offer high levels of protection tailored to the particular system.

5 Conclusion

In this work, a Network-based ML-driven IDS was presented, along with the cybersecurity datasets that were considered. This system can detect abnormal network traffic using a ML model developed based on the data residing in the CICIDS-17 dataset. The proposed system can accurately detect abnormal behaviour when the data come from the same dataset that was also used for testing purposes. However, when being used in practice it may produce false alarms, while some attacks of newer type can go undetected. For this reason, the ML model used as part of the system's configuration can be updated through a semi-automatic process that encompasses the enrichment of the initial training dataset with new elements and the development and selection of the appropriate revised ML model. The experiments made indicated that the above process can increase the performance of the developed NIDS significantly, even when few real data are included in the updated training dataset.

Acknowledgement. This work has been supported by the AI4HEALTHSEC EU project and partially funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 883273. This paper expresses the opinions of the authors and not necessarily those of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained in this paper.

References

1. Khraisat, A., Gondal, I., Vamplew, P., Kamruzzaman, J.: Survey of intrusion detection systems: techniques, datasets and challenges. *Cybersecurity* 2(1), 1-22 (2019).
2. Buczak, A.L., Guven, E.: A survey of data mining and machine learning methods for cyber security intrusion detection. *IEEE Communications surveys & tutorials* 18(2), 1153-1176 (2015).
3. Salo, F., Injadat, M., Nassif, A.B., Shami, A., Essex, A.: Data mining techniques in intrusion detection systems: A systematic literature review. *IEEE Access* 6, 56046-56058 (2018).
4. Liu, H., Lang, B.: Machine learning and deep learning methods for intrusion detection systems: A survey. *Applied Sciences* 9(20), 4396 (2019).
5. Li, J.H.: Cyber security meets artificial intelligence: a survey. *Frontiers of Information Technology & Electronic Engineering* 19(12), 1462-1474 (2018).
6. Shahriari, B., Swersky, K., Wang, Z., Adams, R.P., De Freitas, N.: Taking the human out of the loop: A review of Bayesian optimization. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 104(1), 148-175 (2015).
7. Thornton, C., Hutter, F., Hoos, H.H., Leyton-Brown, K.: Auto-WEKA: Combined selection and hyperparameter optimization of classification algorithms. In: *19th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining Proceedings*, pp. 847-855 (2013).
8. Jain, A.K.: Data clustering: 50 years beyond K-means. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 31(8), 651-666 (2010).
9. Schubert, E., Sander, J., Ester, M., Kriegel, H. P., Xu, X.: DBSCAN revisited, revisited: why and how you should (still) use DBSCAN. *ACM Transactions on Database Systems (TODS)* 42(3), 1-21 (2017).
10. Agrawal, R., Srikant, R.: Fast algorithms for mining association rules. In: *20th International Conference on Very Large Data Bases (VLDB) Proceedings*, pp. 487-499 (1994).
11. Han, J., Pei, J., Yin, Y.: Mining frequent patterns without candidate generation. *ACM sigmod record* 29(2), 1-12 (2000).
12. Chou, D., Jiang, M.: A survey on data-driven network intrusion detection. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 54(9), 1-36 (2021).
13. Tavallaei, M., Bagheri, E., Lu, W., Ghorbani, A.A.: A detailed analysis of the KDD CUP 99 data set. In: *2009 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence for Security and Defense Applications (CISDA) Proceedings*, pp. 1-6. IEEE (2009).
14. Sharafaldin, I., Lashkari, A.H., Ghorbani, A.A.: Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization. In: *4th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy (ICISSP) Proceedings*, pp. 108-116, Portugal (2018).

15. Moustafa, N., Slay, J.: UNSW-NB15: a comprehensive data set for network intrusion detection systems (UNSW-NB15 network data set). In: 2015 military communications and information systems conference (MilCIS) Proceedings, pp. 1–6. IEEE (2015).
16. Cremer, F., Sheehan, B., Fortmann, M., Kia, A. N., Mullins, M., Murphy, F., Materne, S.: Cyber risk and cybersecurity: a systematic review of data availability. *The Geneva Papers on risk and insurance-Issues and practice* 47(3), 698-736 (2022).
17. Alshaibi, A., Al-Ani, M., Al-Azzawi, A., Konev, A., Shelupanov, A.: The comparison of cybersecurity datasets. *Data* 7(2), 22 (2022).
18. Aouini, Z., Pekar, A.: NFStream: A flexible network data analysis framework. *Computer Networks* 204, 108719 (2022).
19. Pekar, A., Jozsa, R.: Evaluating ML-Based Anomaly Detection Across Datasets of Varied Integrity: A Case Study. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.16843* (2024).
20. Fernández, A., Garcia, S., Herrera, F., Chawla, N.V.: SMOTE for learning from imbalanced data: progress and challenges, marking the 15-year anniversary. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research* 61, 863-905 (2018).
21. Stiawan, D., Idris, M.Y.B., Bamhdi, A.M., Budiarto, R.: ICIDS-2017 dataset feature analysis with information gain for anomaly detection. *IEEE Access*. 8, 132911-132921 (2020).